

On The Concept of Algebraic Actions In Neutrosophic Groups

Rozina Ali

Independent researcher, Cairo, Egypt, e-mail: rozyyy123n@gmail.com

Abstract: The objective of this paper is to study the concept of algebraic action on neutrosophic group.

This work defines weak neutrosophic actions and strong neutrosophic actions over a multiplicative neutrosophic group $N(G)$, and presents some of their elementary properties.

Key words: Weak neutrosophic action, strong neutrosophic action, multiplicative neutrosophic group, indeterminacy

1. Introduction

Neutrosophy is a new generalized logic deals with indeterminacy in all the fields of knowledge. It was presented by the American mathematician F.Smarandache in 1995 as a generalization of Fuzzy logic [1].

The algebraic theory of neutrosophy began with the great efforts of Kandasamy and Smarandache, where they proposed the concept of neutrosophic group and neutrosophic ring in [12].

Recently, there is an increasing interest in neutrosophic algebraic structures such as neutrosophic ideals [1,2,17], homomorphisms [8,18,23,25], equations, and number theory [10,27], spaces [3,4,16,21,22], and modules [9,13,14].

Neutrosophic groups were studied widely, especially their substructures such as AH-solvability [7,15], and n -refined nilpotency, normality [11] and graphs [5].

Through this paper, we concentrate on defining actions over this kind of groups as a generalization of classical actions on classical groups. In particular, we present many interesting properties of these actions.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 :[7]

Let $(G,*)$ be a multiplicative group, then the multiplicative neutrosophic group is generated by G and I under $*$ denoted by $N(G) = \langle G \cup I, * \rangle$

I is called the indeterminate element (neutrosophic element) with the property $I^2 = I$.

The most useful understanding of this definition had been written in [2], where we consider $N(G)$ as a union of G and GI , i.e. $N(G) = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_1I, x_2I, \dots; x_i \in G\}$

Definition 2.2 :[7].

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group and H be a neutrosophic subgroup, i.e. (H contains a proper subgroup of G) of $N(G)$, then H is a neutrosophic normal subgroup of $N(G)$ if $xH = Hx$ for all $x \in N(G)$.

Definition 2.3 :[5]

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group. The center of $N(G)$ is denoted by $C(N(G))$ and defined as

$$.C(N(G)) = \{x \in N(G); xy = yx \forall y \in N(G)\}$$

Definition 2.4 : [7]

Let $N(G)$, $N(H)$ be two neutrosophic groups, then $N(G) \times N(H) = \{(g, h); g \in N(G), h \in N(H)\}$

Definition 2.5 :[5]

Let $N(G)$, $N(H)$ be two neutrosophic groups and $\varphi: N(G) \rightarrow N(H)$ is called a neutrosophic homomorphism if it is a homomorphism between G , H , and $\varphi(I) = I'$

Where I' is the neutrosophic element of $N(H)$.

If φ is a correspondence one-to-one it is called a neutrosophic isomorphism.

Theorem 2.1 :[5]

$.G \cong H$ if and only if $N(G) \cong N(H)$

Example 2.1 :

Let $G = (\{1, -1\}, .)$ we must understand $N(G) = \{1, -1, I, -I\}$

Theorem 2.2 :[5]

If G is a finite group, then $O(N(G)) = 2 O(G)$.

Definition 2.6 : [6]

Let G be a group and A be any non empty set, then the well defined map $*$: $G \times A \rightarrow A$ is called an action if

$$\text{and } x * (y * a) = (x y) * a \text{ for all } G \in y, x, A \in a. e * a = a$$

Definition 2.7 : [6]

, is called the stabilizer of a and it is a subgroup of $G. G_a = \{x \in G ; x * a = a\}$

Remark 2. 1: [6]

If H is a subgroup of G , then there is a group homomorphism $f: G \rightarrow S_A$ with $\ker f \leq H$.

3. Actions on neutrosophic groups

Definition 3.1:

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group and A be a non empty set with a fixed element J , let $*$: $N(G) \times A \rightarrow A$ be a Well defined map, we say that $(*)$ is a strong neutrosophic action if the following conditions hold:

$$(a) e * a = a, I * a = a.$$

$$(b) x * (y * a) = (xy) * a \text{ for all } a \in A, x, y \in N(G).$$

We call $(*)$ a weak neutrosophic action if

$$(a) e * a = a, I * J = J$$

$$(b) x * (y * a) = (xy) * a \text{ for all } a \in A, x, y \in N(G).$$

It is clear that every strong action is a weak one.

We call the neutrosophic action $(*)$ transitive if for every $a, b \in A \exists g \in N(G)$ such that $g * a = b$.

Examples 3.1 :

(a) Every neutrosophic group $N(G)$ has a weak action on itself defined by

$$*: N(G) \times N(G) \rightarrow N(G) \text{ with } x * y = xy \text{ for all } x, y \in N(G).$$

(b) Let $H(I)$ be a neutrosophic subgroup of $N(G)$, then it acts strongly on $N(G)$ by

$$\text{with } h * g = hg \text{ for all } h \in H \text{ and } g \in G. *: H(I) \times N(G) \rightarrow N(G)$$

Theorem 3.1 :

If the group G acts on the set A by $*$, then the neutrosophic group $N(G)$ acts strongly on A .

Proof :

Let $(.) : N(G) \times A(I) \rightarrow A(I)$ with $g . a = g * a$ if $g \in G$ and if $g = xI \in GI$ then $xI . a = x * a$.

It is easy to see that the previous map is a strong action because $I * a = a$ for all $a \in A$.

Theorem 3.2 :

If the neutrosophic group $N(G)$ acts on A by strong or weak action, then G acts on A .

Proof :

It is easy to see that the action (*) defined above can be restricted on $G \times A$.

Theorem 3.3 :

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group acts strongly on A , then the relation \wedge defined as

$a \wedge b$ if and only if there is $g \in N(G)$, then $g * a = b$ is a correspondence relation.

Proof :

We have $a \wedge a$ because $e * a = a$, and if we have $a \wedge b$ and $b \wedge c$, then there are $x, y \in N(G)$ such that

hence $y * (x * a) = c$, this implies $(yx) * a = (x * a = b, y * b = c)$, c so that $a \wedge c$.

Now, we assume that $a \wedge b$, then there exists $x \in N(G)$ such that $x * a = b$. If $x \in G$ then $a = x^{-1} * b$.

If $x = yI \in GI$, then $yI * a = b$ so that $I * a = y^{-1} * b = a$ and $b \wedge a$ clearly.

Theorem 3.4 :

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group acts on A by a weak action. The relation \wedge defined as

$(a \wedge b$ if and only if there is $g \in N(G)$ then $g * a = b)$ is reflexive, transitive with the property $a \wedge b$ implies $b \wedge (I * a)$ or $b \wedge a$.

proof :

We have $a \wedge a$ because $e * a = a$, and if we have $a \wedge b$ and $b \wedge c$ then there are $x, y \in N(G)$ such that

$(x * a = b, y * b = c)$ so that $y * (x * a) = c$ thus $(yx) * a = c$ so $a \wedge c$

Now assume that $a \wedge b$ then there is $x \in N(G)$ such $x * a = b$, if $x \in G$, then $a = x^{-1} * b$.

If $x = yI \in GI$, then $yI * a = b$, so that $I * a = y^{-1} * b$ so the proof is complete.

Definition 3.2 :

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group acts on A , for $x \in A$ we define

$$.Orb(x) = \{ g * x ; g \in N(G) \}$$

The stabilizer $G_a = \{ x \in N(G) ; x * a = a \}$.

The kernel of $(*)$ is defined as $\bigcap_{a \in A} G_a$

Theorem 3.5:

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group acts on A by strong or weak action, for any $a \in A$, we have G_a is a neutrosophic subgroup of $N(G)$.

Proof :

By Theorem 3.4, we find that G_a contains the stabilizer subgroup of a in G , thus G_a is a neutrosophic subgroup.

Remark 3.1:

If $(*)$ is a simple neutrosophic action, then it is clear that $I \in G_a$ for all $a \in A$.

Theorem 3.6 :

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group and $H(I)$ be a neutrosophic subgroup of $N(G)$, where H is a subgroup of G , then there is a neutrosophic homomorphism $\varphi : N(G) \rightarrow N(S_A)$ with

$$N(\text{Ker } \varphi) \leq H(I).$$

proof :

G acts on $A = \{ gH ; \in G \}$ by $(*)$ defined as $g * (aH) = (ga)H$, hence there is a group homomorphism $f: G \rightarrow S_A$ with $\text{ker } f \leq H$. This means that we can find a neutrosophic homomorphism $\varphi : N(G) \rightarrow N(S_A)$ with $\varphi_G = f$ and $N(\text{Ker } \varphi) \leq H(I)$.

Conclusion

In this paper, we have studied the concept of algebraic action over multiplicative neutrosophic groups. Many properties were proved in a similar way to the classical concept of actions.

As a future research direction, this work can be extended into refined and n -refined neutrosophic groups respectively, where actions on these kinds of generalized structures are still unknown.

References

[1] Abobala, M., "On Some Special Substructures of Neutrosophic Rings and Their Properties", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science", Vol. 4 , pp. 72-81, 2020.

- [2] Smarandache, F., and Abobala, M., " n -Refined neutrosophic Rings", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol.5 , pp. 83-90 , 2020.
- [3] Abobala, M., "AH-Subspaces in Neutrosophic Vector Spaces", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 6 , pp. 80-86, 2020
- [4] Abobala, M., "A Study of AH-Substructures in n -Refined Neutrosophic Vector Spaces", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science", Vol. 9, pp.74-85, 2020.
- [5]Chalapathi, T and Kumar, K., (2017), neutrosophic graphs of finite groups , neutrosophic sets and systems , vol. 15.
- [6] Haushi M , Algebraic structures , Tishreen university press , 2004 , p.p 112-140
- [7] Ali .M and Smarandache .F., (2015), neutrosophic soluble groups , neutrosophic nilpotent groups and their properties , neutrosophic sets and systems, vol.11.
- [8] Abobala, M., " Classical Homomorphisms Between n -refined Neutrosophic Rings", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science", Vol. 7, pp. 74-78 , 2020.
- [9] Sankari, H., and Abobala, M., " n -Refined Neutrosophic Modules", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 36 , 2020.
- [10] Sankari, H., and Abobala, M.,(2020). Neutrosophic Linear Diophantine Equations With two Variables, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 38, pp. 22-30,.
- [11] Abobala, M. (2019). n -Refined Neutrosophic Groups I, International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 0, pp. 27-34.
- [12] Kandasamy .V and Smarandache ,F., (2006) , Some Neutrosophic Algebraic Structures and Neutrosophic N-Algebraic Structures , Hexis , Phonex , Arizona , p.p 219.
- [13] Alhamido, R., and Abobala, M., (2020), AH-Substructures in Neutrosophic Modules", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 7, pp. 79-86 ,.
- [14] Hatip, A., and Abobala, M., (2020), AH-Substructures In Strong Refined Neutrosophic Modules, International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 9, pp. 110-116 .
- [15] Hatip, A., Alhamido, R., and Abobala, M., (2020), A Contribution to Neutrosophic Groups, International Journal of Neutrosophic Science", Vol. 0, pp. 67-76 , 2019.
- [16] Smarandache F., and Abobala, M., (2020), n -Refined Neutrosophic Vector Spaces, International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 7, pp. 47-54, 2020
- [17] Abobala, M. (2020). On Some Special Substructures of Refined Neutrosophic Rings, International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 5, pp. 59-66.

- [18] Sankari, H., and Abobala, M. (2020). AH-Homomorphisms In Neutrosophic Rings and Refined Neutrosophic Rings, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 38, pp. 101-112,.
- [19] Yingcang, Ma., Xiaohong Zhang ., Smarandache, F., and Juanjuan, Z. (2019). The Structure of Idempotents in Neutrosophic Rings and Neutrosophic Quadruple Rings, Symmetry Journal (MDPI), Vol. 11
- [20] Kandasamy, V. W. B., Ilanthenral, K., and Smarandache, F. (2019). Semi-Idempotents in Neutrosophic Rings, Mathematics Journal (MDPI), Vol. 7.
- [21] Abobala, M. (2020). n -Cyclic Refined Neutrosophic Algebraic Systems Of Sub-Indeterminacies, An Application To Rings and Modules, International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 12, pp. 81-95 .
- [22] Sankari, H., and Abobala, M. (2020). Solving Three Conjectures About Neutrosophic Quadruple Vector Spaces, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 38, pp. 70-77.
- [23] Abobala, M. (2020). Classical Homomorphisms Between Refined Neutrosophic Rings and Neutrosophic Rings, International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 5, pp. 72-75.
- [24] Kandasamy, V., Kandasamy, I., and Smarandache, F., (2018), Neutrosophic Duplets of $\{Z_{p^n}, \times\}$ and $\{Z_{pq}, \times\}$ and Their Properties, Symmetry, vol. 33, pp.18-27.
- [25] Abobala, M. (2020), On Some Special Elements In Neutrosophic Rings and Refined Neutrosophic Rings. Journal Of New Theory. Vol. 33, pp. 33-39 .
- [26] Kandasamy, V., Kandasamy, I., and Smarandache, F., (2018) , Algebraic Structure of Neutrosophic Duplets In Neutrosophic Rings $\langle Z \cup I \rangle$, $\langle Q \cup I \rangle$, and $\langle R \cup I \rangle$, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol.23, pp.85-95.
- [27] Abobala, M. (2020), On Some Neutrosophic Algebraic Equations. Journal Of New Theory. Vol. 33 , pp. 26-32.
- [28] Abobala, M., On Refined Neutrosophic Matrices and Their Applications In Refined Neutrosophic Algebraic Equations, Journal Of Mathematics, Hindawi, 2021
- [29] Abobala, M., A Study of Maximal and Minimal Ideals of n -Refined Neutrosophic Rings, Journal of Fuzzy Extension and Applications, Vol. 2, pp. 16-22, 2021.
- [30] Abobala, M., " Semi Homomorphisms and Algebraic Relations Between Strong Refined Neutrosophic Modules and Strong Neutrosophic Modules", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 39, 2021.

- [31] Abobala, M., On The Representation of Neutrosophic Matrices by Neutrosophic Linear Transformations, Journal of Mathematics, Hindawi, 2021.
- [32] Abobala, M., "On Some Algebraic Properties of n-Refined Neutrosophic Elements and n-Refined Neutrosophic Linear Equations", Mathematical Problems in Engineering, Hindawi, 2021
- [33] Abobala, M., Partial Foundation of Neutrosophic Number Theory, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol.39, 2021.
- [34] Sankari, H, and Abobala, M., " On A New Criterion For The Solvability of non Simple Finite Groups and m-Abelian Solvability, Journal of Mathematics, Hindawi, 2021.
- [35] Abobala, M., "On Some Special Elements In Neutrosophic Rings and Refined Neutrosophic Rings", Journal of New Theory, vol. 33, 2020.
- [36] Sankari, H, and Abobala, M, " A Contribution to m-Power Closed Groups", UMM-Alqura University Journal for Applied Sciences, KSA, 2020.
- [37] Kandasamy V, Smarandache F., and Kandasamy I., Special Fuzzy Matrices for Social Scientists . Printed in the United States of America,2007, book, 99 pages.
- [38] F. Smarandache, *Neutrosophic Theory and Applications*, Le Quy Don Technical University, Faculty of Information technology, Hanoi, Vietnam, 17th May 2016.
- [39] Chakraborty, A., Banik, B., Mondal, S.P., and Alam, S. (2020). Arithmetic and Geometric Operators of Pentagonal Neutrosophic Number and its Application in Mobile Communication Service Based MCGDM Problem, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, vol. 32, pp. 61-79.
- [40] Olgun, N., and Hatip, A. (2020). The Effect Of The Neutrosophic Logic On The Decision Making, in Quadruple Neutrosophic Theory And Applications, Belgium, EU, Pons Editions Brussels,pp. 238-253.